

Preservation and management of research data at the Swedish National Data Service

Date: 2021-11-21

Version: 2

[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0](#)

(CC-BY 4.0)

Swedish National Data Service

snd.gu.se

(+46) 31-786 10 00

snd@gu.se

SND, University of Gothenburg,

Box 463, 405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden

Research data are preserved and managed with the aim of being usable now and in the future. Below is a brief description of the measures taken to ensure this.

Data integrity and long-term preservation

At SND, digital objects are managed in a secure way to ensure future reusability. This includes:

- Virus scan of all submitted files
- Checksums at file level to guarantee data integrity
- Original files are kept in their original file formats, as well as saved in formats suitable for long-term preservation (file conversion if needed)
- All versions of data are preserved, and new versions are automatically assigned a new digital object identifier (DOI)
- Continuous backup (stored in two independent locations)
- Monitoring of file formats to secure that accepted and preferred file formats remain suitable for long-term preservation (migration if needed)
- Updating of metadata as needed, to ensure that data are described in the best way possible, and in a way that makes them understandable and usable over time.

Metadata and documentation

In order to understand and correctly reuse data, it is important to have access to all relevant information. Data are submitted via the SND information system DORIS, which enables a structured description of metadata. Different domains require different metadata, and in DORIS researchers can choose between several domain-specific metadata profiles and a general profile. In addition to a rich data description, it is important to attach other related documentation generated during the research process. This could include, for example, variable lists, code books, questionnaires, publications, study reports, and technical reports.

To make data visible and findable, a catalogue entry is published in the SND research data catalogue. The metadata in the catalogue entry can be harvested by other relevant information platforms, which increases visibility for the data. All metadata that are described and shared via the SND system are applied with a CC0 license.

SND is certified as a Trusted Digital Repository, follows the OAIS Reference Model, and uses established standards and best practices in managing and preserving research data.